

README

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This version of our replication files might be lightly updated upon acceptance of our article.

Overview

We document the replication files of the analysis from our manuscript titled “Perceived synergies and trade-offs between sustainable urban transport objectives with or without autonomous and electric vehicles: Survey results from five Swiss agglomerations”, which we are resubmitting after careful revisions to *PLOS Sustainability and Transformation*.

A first manuscript was submitted on the 30th of July, 2025. We are resubmitting on 31th of March, 2026.

We report the required environment for the computation, our rights to use the data, and the procedure to reproduce our analysis. Specifically, we provide the code to reproduce:

1. pre-processing of the data
2. main analysis and its results (i.e., Table 1 and Figures 3, 4, 5 and 6 in the article)
3. additional tables and figures in the Supporting information or the article (prior and posterior predictive checks and posterior distributions)

The aim is to enable the replication of the analysis by humans and to be transparent and as clear as possible regarding how we conducted our study.

Computational requirements

For the computation, you will need to run the script using R, with several packages required in your local environment.

- **Software:** It is required that you have R installed (R Core Team 2025), and an editor you feel comfortable with (e.g., RStudio). The latest versions we used were 2026.01.1+403 for RStudio and the “Apple Blossom” version (2026-02-04) for R on windows. A C++ compiler is required to use the R package Bayesian regression models using Stan `brms` from Bürkner (2021), see here for guidance.
- **R Packages:** The replication procedure relies on numerous R packages. To facilitate installing the packages, a `renv.lock` file is provided, which lets the you install all the necessary packages by calling `renv::restore()`, using the R package `renv`.

Use of data

We provide in the `/data` folder of this repository the following `.csv` sheet, which is necessary to run the script:

- **Survey data:** The raw survey contained URLs and IP addresses of respondents. We removed URLs and IP addresses to ensure full anonymity of the responses, otherwise the data `anonymized_survey.csv` exactly matches the raw survey data.
 - ☒ The authors certify they have legitimate access and permission to use the above survey data.

Code

The script `main.R` reproduces the analysis and figures from the paper and its supplementary information. The script has a step-by-step structure to facilitate reuse by humans. Basic knowledge of R is expected. `main.R` calls two specific R scripts stored at `scripts/`:

- **Data cleaning:** In `scripts/data_cleaning.R`, we load the data and preprocess the data frame, saving the output as `ev_df.csv` and `av_df.csv` at `data/clean_data`.
- **Analysis and reporting:** With `scripts/analysis.R`, we present the main analysis, which is constituted of cumulative ordinal model fits using `brms` and representation of the most likely perceived impacts using `ggraph`. The script will reproduce Figures 2, 3, 4 and 5 from the article, capturing the results of our main analysis. It also reproduces, in the last part of the script, the production of the figures from the article’s Supplementary Information referring to the Bayesian Analysis Reporting Guidelines (BARG) proposed by Kruschke (2021). Specifically, we detail the following points:
 - 1.E (Prior predictive check),
 - 3.A (Posterior predictive check),
 - 3.B (Summarize posterior of variables),

References

- Bürkner, Paul-Christian. 2021. “Bayesian Item Response Modeling in R with Brms and Stan.” *Journal of Statistical Software* 100 (November): 1–54. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v100.i05>.
- Kruschke, John K. 2021. “Bayesian Analysis Reporting Guidelines.” *Nature Human Behaviour* 5 (10): 1282–91. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-021-01177-7>.
- R Core Team. 2025. “R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing.” Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>.